

A game of thief and dragon

Paul Kinsler*

Department of Electronic & Electrical Engineering, University of Bath, Bath, BA2 7AY, United Kingdom

(Dated: Monday 1st September, 2025)

I introduce a generalised version of shoot-and-scoot applicable to many scenarios where a mobile and active agent attempts to approach and somehow engage with a less mobile one; whilst all the time planning to be able to retreat away from contact before the approached party decides to react in some decisive way. Here I outline the game scenario, which is presented in the style of a boardgame format in order to avoid being overly abstract, and so improve comprehensibility. An analysis is presented looking at the main parameters controlling the strategies of agents on both sides: not only for fixed agent behaviours, but also ones that designed to react to their opponent's actions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Here I propose an “encounter” game mechanism where an agent approaches some target or boundary (here “picket”) in order to stay and achieve some goal, but nevertheless also aims to retreat away before the picket can take any successful counter-action. Here we might imagine a paparazzi trying to stay close some celebrity event without unduly provoking any venue security, or protestors chanting slogans at some event whilst – again – avoiding being apprehended. From the other side, the aim of the venue security is to remain alert and discourage any approach by occasionally taking action, but generally attempting to minimise effort and avoid expensive and heavy handed responses. More whimsically, one might imagine a team of mice trying to annoy some elephants by sneaking close and squeaking loudly; but then having to try to avoid being stepped on by one of the recently panicked pachyderms; or an invisible thief selecting items from a dragon's hoard, but with every chink and clatter giving away more location information to the dragon.

First I will define the game participants and scenario, followed by the key “encounter” mechanism aligned with the examples just given. That done, I define agent algorithms that are used to control each side, and provide an initial exploration of the parameter space, and an analysis of the range of outcomes.

Before proceeding with the mechanics of the encounter interactions, the basic game pieces need to be introduced. Here I will deliberately define the system as if it were a physical board game so as to avoid an overly mathematical or unduly abstract presentation. Indeed it could be played as a game in itself, although play testing would be required to fine-tune the parameters and interaction mechanisms to better represent the intended “skin” (e.g. protestors vs security, thief vs dragon, etc) as well as to ensure the game is interesting to the players. Thus the game proceeds turn by turn, with the actor moving first, followed by the picket; and then that process being repeated until the game is ended.

The game as presented here fall into the general category of attacker-defender games [1], although I paid no particular attention to any existing literature when creating either the idea, its implementation, or doing this investigation.

FIG. 1. Suggested symbols for the Actor's ACT unit counters and PLUS/ZERO markers, as will be used in later figures.

II. DEFINITIONS

Here we will call the agent or player who controls the more active side – that who *advances*, *interjects*, then *retreats* – the “Actor”; and that who controls the more passive side the “Picket”.

In what follows here we will describe the game as if there was a single Actor and a single Picket, which simplifies many details. A more comprehensive description, which describes a sequence of play that can encompass multiple Actors and/or multiple Pickets is intended to be added in a later version of this manuscript, although those sufficiently familiar with boardgames played on tiled maps or sets of linked nodes will likely be able to create something themselves. For games where multiple Actor pieces are managed by a single player or agent, I suggest that that that player/agent are called the “Actrix”; and that for multiple Picket pieces the managing player/agent is called the “Picker”.

A. Actors

- Actors are represented using double-faced unit counters, each face denoting one of the two states: move and stay. A suggestion for the counter designs is shown on fig. 1; the slot in the STAY icon can be used to indicate its orientation towards its target Picket in a spatially distributed game.

- Subject to the details of the rules, an Actor unit can choose from the actions *move*, *wait*, or *interject*. Since the Actor must remain stationary whilst *interjecting*, the period in which they do so can also be called the “dwell” time.

Actors can only move when in their move state (i.e. MOVE face up), and only *interject* when in their stay state (i.e. STAY face up).

To indicate how many turns an actor has been able to *interject* without interruption, we can use additional “PLUS” marker counters, adding one per turn on top of the Actor unit counter to form a growing stack. These PLUS markers should be double-faced, with the reverse being a “zero” state (“ZERO”). This means that when an actor decides to stop *interjecting* and retreat, we can keep the stack of markers in

* <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5744-8146>

FIG. 2. Suggested symbols for the Picket’s PIC unit counters and RESO markers, as will be used in later figures.

place but flipped over. This is necessary since the number of markers is relevant to resolving *responses* by the Picket, and responses are not resolved immediately.

Actors also need a scoring system so that they can determine their level of success. This is discussed below, where successes are counted in KUDOS; but will most plausibly depend positively on the number of turns of *interjections* they apply, and perhaps negatively for each successful *response* (“REBUFF”) the Picket delivers.

B. Pickets

- Pickets are also represented using double-faced unit counters, each face denoting one of the two states: active and passive. However, although it is easy to imagine extra rules that require a passive state – such as a Picket becoming disrupted or distracted by *interjections*, and so being unable to respond – in the below we will mainly ignore this possibility. Further, here we assume that Pickets always stay in a fixed location during the game, as determined by the Picket player or agent at the beginning. A suggestion for the counter designs is shown on fig. 2.

- Subject to the details of the rules, a Picket unit can either *wait* or, if the Actor unit has PLUS or ZERO markers in its stack, initiate a *response*.

To indicate whether or not a *response* has been initiated, the Picket side needs *response* counters (“RESO”) of two sorts: ones that are blank on top and indicate a *response* underneath, and ones that are doubly blank. This enables the Picket player to place RESO counters blank-face up, thus concealing whether or not they actually intend a *response* to the Actor, whilst still leaving their decision choice in-place and safe from overt tampering.

Pickets also need a scoring system so that they can determine their level of success. This is discussed below, but will most plausibly depend negatively on the number of turns of *interjections* they are subject to, and negatively for each unsuccessful *response* they initiate, but positively for each successful *response* (a REBUFF) they deliver.

III. AN ENCOUNTER, AND HOW WE RESOLVE PLAY

A single encounter usually proceeds with a series of *advances* by the Actor (in move state) to some chosen minimum distance, where it flips to the stay state, then dwells for one or more turns whilst persistently *interjecting*. As the number of *interjections* rises, in each turn the Actor must decide whether they should now be satisfied with their achievements so far, flip back to move, then *retreat*; hopefully doing this before the Picket initiates a successful *response*.

At the same time, as the number of *interjections* rises, the Picket might decide that their tolerance has been exhausted,

FIG. 3. A schematic turn-by-turn run through where the Actor approaches a Picket and *interjects* for several turns, then departs without the Picket initiating a *response*. For clarity, we show the PLUS (ZERO) counters only as small symbols adjacent to the Actor unit, rather than the increasingly tall stack that would be present in a physical game. Here the map is a simple linear chain of nodes.

and so initiate a *response*. Two typical encounters between an approaching Actor and a Picket are shown schematically in figs. 3 and 4.

A. Important game choices

Generally speaking, the kind of scenarios this game is designed to mimic is one where both Actors and *responses* are either valuable or in short supply. Thus any encounter will typically involve only one Actor, and the Picket will (or can) only initiate at most a single *response* against that Actor.

Given this, there are now four key elements of the interaction to define. Any or all of these might be set differently, but in the following analysis we only consider these specific choices.

1. How does the Actor consider that their score rises with the number of turns of *interjection*?
 - Here I have decided that the total score rises nonlinearly, and that if the actors is adjacent to the Picket, then as turns pass it increments as 1,3,6,10,15,...; on the x -th

turn of *interjections*, the score increment is x , and so after X turns the accumulated score will be $X(X + 1)/2$. This reflects the idea that the longer the Actor remains in place, they become more effective at achieving their goals.

In what follows we will track the Actors *interjection* score as counted in “KUDOS”, and keep track of the negative – for the Actor – successful Picket responses count in “REBUFF” separately.

2. How does the Picket consider that their tolerance becomes exhausted as the number of turns of *interjection* increases?
 - Here I have decided that this rises linearly with the number of turns, of *interjection* aimed at it, as indicated by the stack of PLUS counters on an *interjecting* Actor.
3. How should we resolve for the success of a Picket’s *response*?

The effect of – and the resolution of – a *response* arrives the turn after it is initiated; it is not instantaneous. It is therefore possible, albeit unlikely, that the Actor will have moved away in the meantime.

 - Here we will simply roll a six-sided dice (a d6), and if the number is less than the number of turns of *interjection*, then the *response* is successful (which we are calling a REBUFF), and that offending Actor is summarily removed from this play.
4. How should we allow for the effect of distance?
 - Here we assume that the Actor’s *interjections* are less effective at range, but that the Picket’s actions are unaffected by range. Specifically, for every 1 extra square or link the Actor is distant from the Picket, the *interjection* score for that turn is reduced by 1; but tolerance checks and *response* success is unaffected.

B. Remarks

At this point we can see that despite rather ruthless attempts to simplify this scenario, there is no small amount of Actor and Picket behavioural detail, even without those that might control and scenario-specific details; and even notwithstanding additional ones we might need for some behavioural algorithm describing an autonomous agent’s tactics. Therefore in what follows we restrict ourselves to some specific choices whilst varying those parameters more likely to have significant effects; and further choose to computational simulate outcomes in order to perform the analysis.

IV. SIMULATED ENCOUNTERS

In order to understand the tradeoffs between parameter choices, particularly the tension between an Actor agent’s *interject* dwell time X and the Picket agent’s tolerance S , I now run Monte Carlo simulations of a series of encounters using different agents. Further, if the simulations contain any adaptive component, these are repeated many times to allow an estimate of the variation in outcomes.

- We assume that a single Actor will approach the Picket once every 15–20 turns, starting a distance of 3 units from the

FIG. 4. A schematic turn-by-turn run through where the Actor approaches a Picket and *interjects* for several turns, but now the Picket initiates a *response*. Here the map is again a simple linear chain of nodes. When played, Picket places a *response* counter blank face up, but since this is not a dummy attack, the other side is RESO. Since the *response* is resolved the following turn, the Actor has accumulated another *interjection* marker; then the Picket flips the RESO marker to reveal that there really was a *response*. Here the *response* is successful and the REBUFFed Actor unit is removed from play, and in turn 9 only the Picket is present. To be properly covert, the Picket player should always play a double-blank marker every turn they do not initiate a *response*, so that the Actor cannot infer a *response* even when a blank is played. Note that if the Actor had instead chosen to flip to MOVE on turn 8, then its unit counter would indeed have been a MOVE, but the stack of PLUS markers would have been also flipped to ZEROS.

Picket, and closing to a not-quite adjacent separation distance of 1. The key parameters we will here vary is the number of turns X which the Actor will spend *interjecting*.

- We assume that there is a single Picket, and that we vary its tolerance S to the Actor’s *interjections*; and that in each encounter the Picket can decide to respond only once.

In the below it is worth noting that there is no unified zero-sum version of “victory”; each agent can have its own criteria. This means that all four combinations of Actor/Picket victory/defeat are possible, both might be satisfied, only one might be, or neither might be; all depending on how each agent might have set their victory conditions. Further, I do not set any such victory conditions, and simply regard an Actor agent who ends up with more KUDOS as better off, and likewise any Picket who achieves more REBUFFs as also bet-

FIG. 5. Results for both Actor and Picket with fixed strategies for X and Tolerance S . Circle sizes increase linearly as the value increases, and are offset from each other to aid visibility.

Actor KUDOSs are double blue squares (maximum 1103), with the sizes differing according to plus or minus one standard deviation in KUDOS counts; the largest circle corresponds to KUDOSS=2800. Likewise, double red circles indicate the number of times and variation in the Picket initiated a *response*, and double black circles the number of REBUFFs (both have maximum values/sizes of 100).

NOTE: This use of double-shapes, sized according to plus or minus one standard deviation from the mean, will be used in most following figures; if only one of a shape is seen, then it is just that the standard deviation is too small to visually separate them.

ter off. Setting specific KUDOS or REBUFF thresholds is a matter of choice for the agents themselves, or for the implementation of an actual game or a scenario within that game. In the below, we can use the figures, and the KUDOS payoffs or response REBUFF rates depicted thereon, as a way of determining how to set parameter (i.e. most simply, either S for the Picket or X for the Actor).

A. Fixed Parameters

For each choice of Actor *interjection* dwell time X and Picket tolerance S , I ran encounter simulations starting with the same Actor and Picket states; the results are shown on fig. 5. We see that there are regions where $X < S$ and that the Picket never responds, this might sometimes be good for the Actor, but not if it was unable to score as highly as it would have liked. On the other hand, for low tolerances the Picket may have suppressed some *interjections*, but the success rate was low, and Actors who avoided the *response* could then continue to *interject* with impunity until its limit of X turns had elapsed.

A comparison of the key results is shown in fig. 5, where we see that the highest return for the Actor occurs unsurprisingly for $X = 7$ and $S = 6$, i.e. long dwell times and high Picket tolerance. However this also comes at a cost for the Actor, since Picket then also achieves successes; but the Actor could avoid these with a dwell time X of 5.

While this scan over fixed X, S Actor and Picket strategies

is not without its uses, in an iterated game we would expect that both sides would try to adjust their behavioural parameters so as to better their goals; and so in what follows we investigate this possibility.

B. Adaption

It is useful to consider agents who can adapt according to the results of each encounter. In what follows each agent can choose to alter their parameters after some learning event, according to a parameter R which represents their aversion to risk taking.

For an Actor, there are two types of learning events, with different and opposite reactions.

1. When a successful *response* (a REBUFF) was achieved against them by the Picket, the actor will reduce their planned dwell (*interjection* time X) by one; so that next time they will leave before a response, or at least decrease the likelihood of any REBUFF.
2. When no successful *response* was taken against them by the Picket, the actor will sometimes increase their planned dwell (*interjection* time X) by one, according to the Actor's risk aversion parameter R_A . This enables the Actor to explore the possibility that it is not currently testing the true limits of the Picket's tolerance, but at the risk of being exposed to more responses from the Picket.

For a Picket, there are also two types of learning events, again with different and opposite reactions.

1. When an unsuccessful *response* was enacted by them against the Actor, they will increase their tolerance S by one; so that next time their *response* is more likely to work.
2. When no *response* was initiated by them against the Actor, they will sometimes decrease their tolerance, according to the Picket's risk aversion parameter R_P . This enables the Picket to see if earlier responses can push the Actor into a shorter dwell time; but at the risk of wasting responses that end up unsuccessful.

Note that both learning responses based on risk aversion will act to *increase* the number of responses from the Picket; either because the Actor dwells longer and tests the Picket's patience more, or because the Picket becomes less tolerant and responds sooner.

Further to this, there are two algorithms used – by either agent – to determine whether this “sometimes” generates an adaptive change to their encounter parameters. Both algorithms generate – on average – the same number of adaptations for the same number of learning events, but one is randomised, and the other deterministic. Essentially, the higher the value of an agent's R parameter, the less likely it is to adapt in an assertive manner; thus R is a measure of aversion to risk.

The algorithms are:

Random: here the agent adapts after learning events according to probability $p = 1/R_A$ or $1/R_P$.

Cyclic: here the agent adapts only after fixed numbers of learning events R_A and R_P have passed.

FIG. 6. Results for adaptive Actor and fixed Picket. Circle sizes increase linearly as the value increases, and are offset from each other to aid visibility. Actor KUDOSs are double blue squares (maximum 1103), with the sizes differing according to the standard deviation in KUDOS. Likewise, Picket *response* counts and variation are double red circles (max 21) and REBUFF are double black circles (max 14). The green bars indicate the one and two standard deviation ranges in final actor X values. The “averages” data for this figure is given in Table I.

It is important to note that the agents only adapt in response to *in-game* events, and not according to (e.g.) some knowledge or belief that their opponent has changed their tactical parameters (such as dwell time X , tolerance S , or their risk aversion R).

C. Adaptive Actor, Fixed Picket

Here we allow an adaptive Actor with $R_A = 5$ who, on being successfully responded to (REBUFFed) by the Picket, will decrease their dwell/*interjection* time X . However, to avoid a run of bad luck forcing their chosen X down to a minimum, they will sometimes (at $p = 1/R_A = 0.2$) increase X if not successfully responded to.

A comparison of the key results is shown in fig. 6 and on table I; these are Monte Carlo-ed over 1000 instances of 100 serial encounters.

We see that the Picket’s REBUFF to *response* ratio improves as S increases from 2, except when $S = 6$ where the Actor always departs before any response is triggered. Otherwise, as the set value of S increases, the Actor adapts by increasing X , providing it with ever greater payoffs; graphically the knee from $S=3$ to 4 appears as the more significant threshold.

D. Adaptive Picket, Fixed Actor

Now we return the Actor to fixed behaviour, and scan X , but allow the Picket to adapt its tolerance S with its risk aversion set by $R_P = 5$. Thus this Picket will increase its tolerance if

X	c	S	r	b
2.189	358.037	1	100	37.85
2.232	385.481	2	100	27.403
2.409	451.757	3	39.575	16.554
3.27	731.957	4	28.698	15.696
4.203	1103.6	5	20.72	13.957
5	1500	6	0	0

TABLE I. Data averages corresponding to fig. 6, i.e. for a fixed Picket and an adaptive Actor. KUDOS c , responses r , successful responses (i.e. REBUFF) b .

FIG. 7. Results for adaptive Picket and fixed Actor. Circle sizes increase linearly as the value increases, and are offset from each other to aid visibility. Actor KUDOSs are double blue squares (maximum 1739), with the sizes differing according to the standard deviation in KUDOS. Likewise, Picket *response* counts and REBUFF are double red circles (max 100) and REBUFF are double black circles (max 100). The green bars indicate the one and two standard deviation ranges in Picket tolerance values. The “averages” data for this figure is given in Table II.

a *response* is unsuccessful, but also decrease it – 20% of the time – if it did not respond to a sequence of *interjections*.

A comparison of the key results is shown in fig. 7 and on table II. These are Monte Carlo-ed over 1000 instances of 100 serial encounters.

We see that the Picket’s REBUFF to *response* ratio reliably improves as the setting of X increases; since the Picket adapts by bringing its tolerance S down close to the dwell time X . It is an interesting feature that the tolerance S starts reducing as dwell time is set higher at 6 or 7; leading to almost perfect response rates.

E. Adaptive Actor and Picket

Here we pit two adaptive agents head to head in a series of encounters, each series being with a different combination of Actor risk aversion R_A and Picket risk aversion R_P . In figure 8 we see that if both agents have these randomised learning adaptations to risk, then regardless of the specific R_A and R_P

X	c	S	r	b
1	100	1.847	12.421	0
2	300	2.844	15.411	2.519
3	600	3.813	19.755	6.594
4	1000	4.77	26.051	12.846
5	1500	5.678	40.898	29.378
6	1831.776	5.228	91.462	88.803
7	1739.601	4	100	100

TABLE II. Data averages corresponding to fig. 7, i.e. for a fixed Actor and an adaptive Picket. KUDOS c , responses r , successful responses (i.e. REBUFF) b .

the long-term outcomes are very similar. Notably, the Actor’s X tends to settle around 3.5, and the Picket’s tolerance about 1 higher at between 4.2 and 4.5. This difference is because the Actor agent always backs off (reduces X) on a successful response (REBUFF), whilst the Picket agent does the same (increases S) on a failed response; thus both jostle each other around a position where successful responses (REBUFF) are likely, but not certain. Then the scoring (whether in KUDOS or REBUFF) then quite naturally also find a quasi-equilibrium around this point. Remarkably, even comparing the results for $R_A = 7$ and $R_P = 1$ to those of $R_A = 1$ and $R_P = 7$ shows little difference; likely because the multiple sources of randomness blur the outcomes enough so that fine distinctions are impossible.

On the other hand, if both agents have cyclic learning adaptations, then there is a much greater variation in the outcomes; as can be seen on figure 9. Unsurprisingly, a cautious Actor with large R_A will score less well, but then it also suffers less; we see that an aggressive Picket with small R_P will have a low fraction of REBUFF successes against them. The contrasting situation of risk-taking Actor (low R_A) and cautious Picket – also unsurprisingly – gives the Actor good returns and the Picket not. The doubly-cautious case of larger R_A and R_P shows quite a wide variation in both Actor returns and Picket REBUFFs.

Contrasting adaption algorithms can also be tested, i.e. where we pit a cyclic adaption against a randomised one. We can see the two comparisons (cyclic Actor vs random Picket, and random Actor vs cyclic Picket) on figures 10 and 11. Here we see that in both cases the outcomes depend primarily on the risk aversion of the cyclically-adapting agent.

F. Adaptive Actor and Picket – initial conditions

According to the standard initial conditions use in the Monte Carlo simulations, both the Actor and Picket cyclic counters start each series of encounters at zero. This leaves open the question of whether starting with an *offset* between the counters has any effect, especially since one agent might have a first-mover advantage (or perhaps a disadvantage) over the other. Further, if both R_A and R_P were equal, then one might expect any advantage to persist and so strongly affect the results. However, since the counters are incremented in *response* to different outcomes, any such offset effect will tend to be disrupted by the stochasticity of the *response* resolution; i.e. in the longer term, the counters have no guarantee of maintaining any fixed relationship.

FIG. 8. Results for adaptive Actor and Picket; spanning different risk aversions, i.e. but adapting after learning events according to probability $p = 1/R_A$ or $1/R_P$. These results change very little, despite the changing parameters. Actor KUDOSs are double blue squares (average 900 KUDOS), with the sizes differing according to the standard deviation in KUDOS. Likewise, Picket *response* counts and variation are double red circles (average 26) and REBUFF are double black circles (average about 13.5).

Nevertheless, it is possible to see such initial-condition effects over a short sequence of repeat encounters. In fig. 12 we set up a scenario involving $n = 6$ encounters, $X = S = 3$, risk aversions of $R_A = R_P = 10$, and test outcomes for all possible combinations of d_A and d_P . As expected, for small $d < R - n$, the results are identical since risk-taking is not/rarely triggered, but beyond that the Picket’s response rate increases, as expected. However, note that if the number of encounters is increased significantly, then the relationship between the Actor’s and the Picket’s risk counters will not persist, and so the outcomes become ever more similar.

V. SUMMARY

I have presented an abstracted board game mechanism that can be mapped on to a range of real-world scenarios, such as a protesters-vs-security situation pitting two agents on opposing sides against each other. Although board games – as implemented here – tend to introduce artificialities such as discrete spatial steps and dice-roll outcomes that in principle might be avoided, they do have the advantage that such “realistic” detail does not then overwhelm the rest of the description, enabling the underlying tradeoffs in the situation to be exposed.

Nevertheless, since even the simple mechanism presented here is not very amenable to any mathematical solution, expected outcomes were generated in repeated 1-vs-1 playoffs by Monte-Carlo methods for a range of simple (fixed) and adaptive agent tactics. A range of agent tactics and parameter ranges were evaluated, demonstrating that outcomes were most sensitive to any choice of deterministic tactics (i.e. fixed behaviour or cyclic adaption).

There is undoubtedly a utility in the comparison of tactical approaches as has been done here; notably that the adap-

FIG. 9. Results for adaptive Actor and Picket; spanning different risk aversions but adapting after fixed numbers of learning events R_A and R_P . Actor KUDOSs are double blue squares (maximum 1345 KUDOS), with the sizes changing according to the standard deviation in KUDOS. Likewise, Picket *response* counts and variation are double red circles (maximum 72) and REBUFF are double black circles (maximum 44).

FIG. 11. Results for adaptive Actor and Picket; spanning different risk aversions, with a cyclic adapting Picket, but a randomly adapting Actor. As usual, Actor KUDOSs are double blue squares, with the sizes changing according to the standard deviation in KUDOS. Picket *response* counts are red circles and REBUFF are black circles.

FIG. 10. Results for adaptive Actor and Picket; spanning different risk aversions, with a cyclic adapting Actor, but a randomly adapting Picket. As usual, Actor KUDOSs are double blue squares, with the sizes changing according to the standard deviation in KUDOS. Picket *response* counts are red circles, and REBUFFs are black circles.

tion of a randomised adaptive strategy should enable an agent to eventually find its sweet spot when pitted against an adversary. One can certainly imagine variations on the simple adaptive schemes suggested here that could tilt the outcomes more towards (e.g.) desired payoffs in terms of KUDOS for Actors or REBUFFs for Pickets.

However, as always with these simple encounter models, there are two significant problems that remain unaddressed. First, most games do not consist of hundreds or thousands of

FIG. 12. Results for adaptive Actor and Picket; starting with equal patience, i.e. dwell time $X = 3$ and tolerance $S = 3$. adapting after learning events cyclically according to event thresholds $R_A = 9$ and $R_P = 10$. Unlike previous results, these are for a small number of encounters (6), allowing the outcomes to depend on initial conditions; i.e. here the starting state of the event counters d_A, d_P .

repetitions, so that any agent – whether human or algorithmic – never has the chance to really optimise their tactics for their opponent; although one might imagine real-world automated scenarios that have large numbers of similar encounters between mass-produced agents. Second, any attempt to decide in advance on a set of tactics – perhaps in concert with simulation (as here) or mathematical analysis – requires an agent to also have a model of the adversary; and such a model might not be either very accurate, nor be of an appropriate level of

complexity. Indeed, it might be said that a good adversary model is as important as a determinant of success as analyses of the type presented in this work.

One of the Challenge topics discussed was relevant to this game idea, and spurred me to construct and develop this model in order to do this brief investigation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author would like to acknowledge the role of the Maths of EMA workshop run by the Newton Institute in early 2025.

-
- [1] K. Hunt and J. Zhuang, A review of attacker-defender games: Current state and paths forward, *European Journal of Operational Research* **313**, 401 (2024).